

SELMA3D 2026: Self-supervised learning for 3D light-sheet microscopy image segmentation: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

SELMA3D 2026: Self-supervised learning for 3D light-sheet microscopy image segmentation

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

SELMA3D 2026

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

In modern biological and biomedical research, high-resolution, 3D visualization of biological structures is essential for understanding spatial organization and structural relationships across scales, yet traditional imaging often fails to offer cellular resolution or preserve tissue integrity. Combining tissue clearing with light-sheet microscopy (LSM) enables high-contrast, ultra-high-resolution imaging of whole organs or even whole organisms [1–3], supporting studies in neuroscience, immunology, oncology, and cardiology [4–7]. A key bottleneck in translating these rich datasets into biological insight lies in automated image analysis, with segmentation serving as a fundamental step. Whole-organ LSM datasets may contain volumes on the order of 10000^3 voxels, making manual annotation infeasible. Deep learning-based segmentation models offer promising automation [8–10], but they remain task-specific, annotation-intensive, and limited in generalizability [11], highlighting the need for scalable solutions.

It is crucial to develop generalizable or foundation models capable of serving multiple LSM image segmentation tasks. Self-supervised learning (SSL) offers significant advantages in this regard, as it allows deep learning models to pretrain on large-scale, unannotated datasets, thereby learning robust and transferable representations of LSM image data. Subsequently, the model can be fine-tuned on relatively small annotated datasets to address specific segmentation tasks [12], substantially reducing annotation burden while improving generalization across datasets and imaging conditions. As a result, robust and scalable segmentation models can directly facilitate a wide range of downstream biological and clinical workflows, including cell counting, axon tracing, vascular network reconstruction, spatial phenotyping, and quantitative morphometric analysis. Beyond segmentation, SSL-pretrained models can also be leveraged for other downstream tasks, such as artifact removal, image deblurring, anomaly detection, cell-type classification, atlas-based mapping and so on. While these applications are certainly interesting and promising, the focus of this challenge is on segmentation.

Despite the availability of extensive LSM datasets encompassing diverse biological structures, SSL remains underexplored in the LSM domain. Notably, certain characteristics of LSM images, such as their high signal-to-noise ratio, make them particularly well-suited for SSL. The SELMA3D challenge represents a significant advancement in SSL research within the field of 3D LSM images. To the best of our knowledge, SELMA3D 2024 was the first attempt to systematically benchmark self-supervised learning approaches for LSM image segmentation. SELMA3D was successfully organized again at MICCAI in 2025, featuring progressively larger datasets, a refined challenge design, and enhanced participant support. However, the scale of the datasets which reached several terabytes, posed a significant barrier, limiting participation and constraining timely method development.

In the 2026 edition, we will build upon the 2025 framework while lowering the entry barrier and advancing the research scope by restructuring SELMA3D into two complementary tasks. These tasks are designed to isolate two central research questions in SSL for 3D LSM: method development under tightly controlled data conditions, and performance scaling under open-data conditions.

Task 1 SSL for 3D LSM image segmentation under fixed training data conditions. To make participation substantially easier and to enable clean methodological comparisons, Task 1 will be run on a fixed, fully prepared dataset. Compared to 2024 and 2025 editions where we provided large, original large 3D LSM images as the unannotated dataset for SSL, this year we will instead offer preprocessed patches. These patches are cropped from the original 3D LSM volumes into a standardized patch size. To reduce data transfer overhead and minimize the time and effort required for large-scale data downloading and preprocessing, the majority of non-informative background regions are filtered out to improve computational efficiency. However, a representative subset, approximately 5% per biological structure, is intentionally retained to preserve realistic low-signal conditions and enable robustness evaluation. This strategy maintains practical feasibility while allowing participants to focus on optimizing their SSL approaches rather than on extensive data handling and preprocessing. To ensure that performance improvements can be attributed to SSL strategy and model design rather than data volume or curation, no additional data will be permitted beyond what is provided in the challenge package. This task is explicitly designed as a controlled benchmark to study SSL method development, including pretext objectives, masking/augmentation strategies, network architectures, and fine-tuning protocols, without confounding effects from heterogeneous external datasets or unequal compute/data access.

Task 2 SSL for 3D LSM image segmentation under open data conditions. In contrast, Task 2 is designed as an open-data challenge in which participants may leverage any amount of data, including the full set of original unannotated 3D LSM images we provide via links, as well as any additional public or private LSM data. Importantly, Task 2 will use the same held-out test set as Task 1, enabling a direct, apples-to-apples assessment of how data scaling and data diversity impact SSL performance, when the evaluation target remains fixed. This design allows the community to quantify the practical gains from increasing pretraining data size and breadth, and to probe whether scaling laws observed in other domains translate to 3D microscopy.

In the 2026 edition, we will also strengthen the challenge's scientific scope by expanding data diversity and difficulty. Beyond the growth in our existing collections, a key novelty is the inclusion of axon-focused LSM data from the BRAIN Initiative CONNECTS program (<https://www.brain-connects.org/>), which introduces fine-grained,

elongated neuronal morphology and new sources of heterogeneity that are not well captured by previously included structures [17]. This axonal data complements the broader expansion of unannotated and annotated samples and provides an important new testbed for SSL generalization in settings where topology and continuity can be particularly challenging. Besides, in this way, SELMA3D 2026 will bring the connectomics and large-scale light-sheet microscopy communities together into MICCAI, bridging traditionally separate research ecosystems.

Moreover, this year beyond differences in connectivity among biological structures, we explicitly consider spatial density and crowding as an additional dimension of spatial complexity during evaluation. For example, cell nuclei typically exhibit a dense pattern, whereas amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) plaques are relatively sparse; similarly, single axons are sparse structures, while brain vessels often form dense networks. Accordingly, this year the datasets are further stratified into four categories: isolated sparse, isolated dense, contiguous sparse, and contiguous dense structures. Model performance will be evaluated separately across these groups, providing deeper insight into where models generalize effectively and where challenges remain.

Building on these improvements, we aim to optimize the challenge setting and establish a more advanced benchmark for self-supervised learning in 3D LSM image segmentation. We look forward to organizing the third edition of the SELMA3D challenge and welcoming submissions.

References:

- [1] E.H.K. Stelzer, F. Strobl, B. Chang, et al. Light sheet fluorescence microscopy. *Nature Reviews Methods Primers* 1(1): 73, 2021 Nov.
- [2] H.R. Ueda, A. Ertürk, K. Chung, et al. Tissue clearing and its applications in neuroscience. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience* 21(2): 61-79, 2020, Jan.
- [3] P.K. Poola, M.I. Afzal, Y. Yoo, et al. Light sheet microscopy for histopathology applications. *Biomedical engineering letters* 9: 279-291, 2019 July.
- [4] H.R. Ueda, H.U. Dodt, P. Osten, et al. Whole-brain profiling of cells and circuits in mammals by tissue clearing and light-sheet microscopy. *Neuron*, 106(3): 369-387, 2020 May.
- [5] D. Zhang, A.H. Cleveland, E. Krimtza, et al. Spatial analysis of tissue immunity and vascularity by light sheet fluorescence microscopy. *Nature Protocols*: 1-30, 2024 Jan.
- [6] J. Almagro, H.A. Messal, M.Z. Thin, et al. Tissue clearing to examine tumour complexity in three dimensions. *Nature Reviews Cancer*, 21(11): 718-730, 2021 July.
- [7] P. Fei, J. Lee, R.R.S.Packard, et al. Cardiac light-sheet fluorescent microscopy for multi-scale and rapid imaging of architecture and function. *Scientific Reports* 6: 22489, 2016 Mar.
- [8] F. Amat, B. Höckendorf, Y. Wan, et al. Efficient processing and analysis of large-scale light-sheet microscopy data. *Nature protocols* 10: 2015: 1679-1696, 2015 Oct.
- [9] N. Kumar, P. Hrobar, M. Vagenknecht, et al. A Light sheet fluorescence microscopy and machine learning-based approach to investigate drug and biomarker distribution in whole organs and tumors. *bioRxiv* 2023.09.16.558068.
- [10] M.I. Todorov, J.C. Paetzold, O. Schoppe, et al. Machine learning analysis of whole mouse brain vasculature. *Nature Methods* 17: 442-449, 2020 Mar.
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- [12] R. Krishnan, P. Rajpurkar, E.J. Topol. Self-supervised learning in medicine and healthcare. *Nature Biomedical Engineering* 6: 1346-1352, 2022 Aug.

- [13] M. Belle, D. Godefroy, C. Dominici, et al. A simple method for 3D analysis of immunolabeled axonal tracts in a transparent nervous system. *Cell reports* 9(4): 1191-1201, 2014 Nov.
- [14] M. Belle, D. Godefroy, G. Couly, et al. Tridimensional visualization and analysis of early human development. *Cell* 169(1): 161-173, 2017 Mar.
- [15] R. Blain, G. Couly, E. Shotar, et al. A tridimensional atlas of the developing human head. *Cell* 186(26): 5910-5924, 2023 Dec.
- [16] <https://mab3d-atlas.com/validated-antibody-database>
- [17] <https://braininitiative.nih.gov/research/neuroimaging-technologies-across-scales/brain-initiative-connectivity-across-scales>.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Light-sheet microscopy, 3D image, deep learning, self-supervised learning, model pretraining, image segmentation, foundation models

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

The SELMA3D challenge is the first benchmark dedicated to self-supervised learning for 3D LSM image segmentation. The challenge emphasizes self-supervised learning, which reduces the reliance on extensive manual annotations by pretraining on large unannotated datasets and fine-tuning on smaller labeled sets.

SELMA3D 2026 marks the third edition of the challenge. This year, continuing the same focus, we introduce a two-task setting under fixed training data and open training data conditions, allowing us to disentangle methodological benchmarking from data-scaling effects. Moreover, based on both morphological characteristics and spatial density, common biological structures in LSM are classified into four categories: isolated sparse, isolated dense, contiguous sparse, and contiguous dense. We will evaluate model performance separately across these categories to provide a more comprehensive assessment of generalization capacity and segmentation difficulty across varying structural complexities. Last but not least, this year, we further expand the dataset by including axon LSM data, which introduces fine-grained, elongated neuronal morphologies and additional sources of heterogeneity not captured by previously included structures. By doing so, SELMA3D 2026 also aims to bring together the connectomics and large-scale LSM communities within MICCAI, bridging traditionally separate research ecosystems.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

While the downstream task for the self-supervised learning of 3D light-sheet microscopy images in this challenge is segmentation, the pretrained model or self-supervised learning strategy can be leveraged for a variety of other downstream tasks, such as object detection, deblurring, stitching, anomaly detection, image denoising and so on.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

No associated workshop.

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

During the SELMA3D challenges held in 2024 and 2025, a total of 143 participants registered. Following the conclusion of these editions, we received additional registrations and expressions of interest from prospective participants, indicating strong potential for increased participation. With growing attention on self-supervised learning (SSL) pre-training, particularly driven by the rise of large vision models, we anticipate even greater engagement in the upcoming edition. To further enhance visibility, we will launch a coordinated social media campaign across LinkedIn, Bluesky, and X to promote the challenge. For SELMA3D 2026, we expect approximately 120 registered participants.

Over the past two years, high registration numbers did not translate into high submission rates. Participants reported that the massive dataset, exceeding 4 TB, posed a significant barrier to model development and final submissions. Guided by this feedback, we redesigned SELMA3D 2026 into two tasks that separate methodological innovation from data scaling effects. In particular, SELMA3D 2026 will substantially lower the entry barrier in Task 1 by providing a fully preprocessed, chunked, and size-reduced dataset of carefully selected yet highly expressive 3D image patches. By delivering a ready-to-use benchmark, where the majority of non-informative background patches have already been removed and volumes are provided in standardized patches, participants can focus their effort on SSL method development rather than data curation and engineering. We will still release reference utilities and documentation for transparency and reproducibility, but the default workflow will require minimal data handling. We anticipate increased participation and substantially more final submissions, especially in this controlled Task 1 setting.

For Task 2, where participants may leverage additional data and study the effect of scaling, we will again provide preprocessing code to assist with dataset handling, e.g. for cropping sequential slices into 3D patches. The preprocessing code is available at: https://github.com/YingChen7/SELMA3D2025_volume_cutting.

The introduction of an axon segmentation task is expected to bring new participants from the connectomics and light-sheet microscopy communities, where the volume of available data is rapidly increasing but robust automated analysis methods remain limited. The lack of established benchmarks and the growing demand for scalable axon segmentation solutions make this task highly relevant and timely, and we anticipate that it will lead to increased submissions, particularly from groups newly entering the SELMA3D challenge ecosystem.

Additionally, we will launch the challenge webpage and begin promotional activities earlier. In the previous

edition, the delayed release of the webpage constrained outreach efforts and limited the time available for teams to develop solutions despite strong interest. This year, we will initiate outreach sooner and release the training dataset earlier, providing participants with ample time to develop and refine their algorithms.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Yes, we plan to summarize and present the challenge results from both 2024, 2025 and 2026 in a journal article. In addition, the axon segmentation task introduced in SELMA3D 2026 will be accompanied by another publication focused on task-specific methodological insights and biological relevance. This manuscript will be submitted to a venue that is widely read by the connectomics and large-scale neuroscience imaging communities, thereby increasing the visibility of MICCAI challenges beyond the traditional medical image analysis audience and fostering cross-community engagement.

The SELMA3D 2024 challenge results have been summarized in a pre-print on arXiv[1].

[1] Y. Chen, R. Al-Maskari, I. Horvath et al. SELMA3D challenge: Self-supervised learning for 3D light-sheet microscopy image segmentation. arXiv:2501.03880, 2025.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

No

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team ([miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de](mailto:micca-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de)) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

The challenge will be hosted on grand-challenge.org. Participants are expected to utilize their own computing resources for algorithm development. Organizers will employ grand-challenge.org for evaluation during the testing phases.

Regarding the in-person event, we require projectors, microphones, loudspeakers, and cameras to facilitate

potential hybrid participation.

TASK 1: Self-supervised learning for 3D LSM image segmentation under fixed training data conditions

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

When combined with tissue clearing and immunostaining, light-sheet microscopy (LSM) has unique advantages for imaging large and intact samples with cellular resolution while minimizing photobleaching and phototoxicity. This makes LSM a powerful tool for visualizing a variety of biological structures and studying their functions and developmental processes.

Task 1 is dedicated to developing self-supervised learning (SSL) strategies for 3D LSM image segmentation under fixed training data conditions. Participants are restricted to using the provided, processed image data for methodology development. The images encompass a wide range of biological structures in LSM. As in the 2025 edition, these biological structures can be categorized into two types: isolated structures and contiguous structures. Isolated structures are spatially distinct, unconnected components, such as cell nuclei, c-Fos+ cells, or pathological formations like amyloid-beta plaques. Contiguous structures, in contrast, are physically continuous, connected structures, such as blood vessels or nerves. Based on the insights from the 2025 edition, this year we will combine both structure types together in the training set, fully exploring the potential of SSL strategies for robust representation learning across diverse biological structures. However, different from the 2025 edition, in Task 1, we will provide cropped, unannotated patches for SSL rather than the original raw 3D LSM images.

A major addition for 2026 is the inclusion of axon-focused LSM data. Specifically, we will incorporate a large LSM dataset generated as part of the Connectivity across Scales (CONNECTS) program [17], one of the three transformative projects of the NIH BRAIN Initiative. The BRAIN CONNECTS program is a \$150M investment towards scaling up methods for imaging the wiring of the brain at microscopic resolutions, with the aim of processing large brain volumes, and ultimately whole brains. In this program, the development of robust, automated segmentation approaches that can scale efficiently and transfer across datasets, species, and experimental conditions would be a major contribution towards this aim. In SELMA3D 2026, we will include a pilot CONNECTS dataset that consists of ultra-high-resolution 3D LSM images of sections stained with axonal markers, including NEFH, NEFL, and parvalbumin (PV), from both macaque and human brains. The cross-species data and fine-scale axonal morphology introduce substantial structural complexity and heterogeneity, making itself particularly well suited for benchmarking the scalability and generalization capability of SSL methods.

Another key update this year is the explicit inclusion of spatial density, alongside connectivity, as a defining characteristic of biological structures. Accordingly, we organize all structures into four categories: isolated sparse, isolated dense, contiguous sparse, and contiguous dense. Performance will be assessed separately within each category, allowing for a more refined evaluation of model generalization and clearer identification of strengths and limitations across varying structural complexities.

In general, for Task 1, participants will be provided with a training dataset consisting of two subsets:

1. Unannotated subset: a large collection of patches cropped and preprocessed from large 3D LSM images of both isolated sparse, isolated dense, contiguous sparse, and contiguous dense structures derived from multiple specimens. This subset includes more than 35,050 patches of size 300×300×300 voxels. These unannotated patches are intended for model pretraining using SSL, allowing models to learn generalizable representations of diverse biological structures.
2. Annotated subset: a curated selection of 3D LSM image patches representing the same isolated sparse, isolated dense, contiguous sparse, and contiguous dense structures in the unannotated subset, but with precise manual annotations, totalling over 210 patches of size 200×200×200 voxels. This subset enables participants to fine-tune their models for the general segmentation of different structures, leveraging the pre-training phase.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Light-sheet microscopy, 3D image, deep learning, self-supervised learning, image segmentation, isolated structure, contiguous structure, sparse structure, dense structure

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

[Helmholtz Munich, Germany]

Ali Erturk, Luciano Höher, Rami Al-Maskari

[Cornell University, New York, USA]

Johannes C. Paetzold, Zhuhao Wu

[Institut de la Vision, Paris, France]

Yorick Gitton, Alain Chedotal

[Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich, Germany]

Ying Chen, Qi Liu

[Athinoula A. Martinos Center for Biomedical Imaging, Massachusetts General Hospital and Harvard Medical School, Massachusetts, USA]

Kyriaki-Margarita Bintsi, Anastasia Yendiki

[Columbia University, New York, USA]

Emine Özen, Elizabeth Hillman

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Ying Chen (Ying.Chen@campus.lmu.de), Johannes C. Paetzold (jop4027@med.cornell.edu), Kyriaki-Margarita Bintsi (kbintsi@mgh.harvard.edu)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

No

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event as open call challenge

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

SELMA3D 2024 website: <https://selma3d.grand-challenge.org/>; SELMA3D 2025 website:

<https://selma3d2025.grand-challenge.org/>; SELMA3D 2026 website: will come later and also appear on the SELMA3D 2025 website

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

User interaction is allowed for data preprocessing. Participants are free to choose their own image preprocessing approaches for both the unannotated and annotated patches used in model pretraining and fine-tuning.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify

whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants are restricted to utilize the training data provided exclusively in this task, which comprises two subsets. The first subset is designated for self-supervised learning and encompasses a large collection of unannotated 3D LSM patches covering diverse biological structures and specimens. The second subset includes a few annotated patches representing the same biological structures, which participants may use to fine-tune their models for the downstream segmentation task.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The challenge webpage will publicly acknowledge the top 3 teams, and they will receive a Jellycat Selma SLOTH as a souvenir during the in-person challenge event. However, no monetary awards will be granted.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All performance results will be disclosed publicly after submission, and outstanding submissions will be acknowledged during the in-person challenge event. However, participating teams have the option to decide whether to make their results public any time prior to the announcement. The top 5 teams will be invited to prepare a 5-10 minute presentation for the challenge session.

Participants who wish to retract their submissions can opt for their performance to be reported anonymously online and in the publication, or they can request complete removal from the leaderboard and publication.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

We plan to collaborate closely with participants to produce a comprehensive journal article summarizing the key results and analyses derived from SELMA3D 2024, SELMA3D 2025 and SELMA3D 2026 challenges. All participating teams that submit work contributing to the algorithm development are welcome to contribute to our challenge publication. Up to three authors from each participating team will be acknowledged as authors of the article. Any additional authors from the submissions may be included upon request according to the ICMJE authorship guidelines.

Furthermore, we encourage all participating teams to independently submit their results without imposing any publication embargo.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Submissions for evaluation on both the preliminary and the final test sets will be done through submitted docker containers, i.e. type 2 submissions on Grand Challenge. Submitted containers will be evaluated by organizers on grand-challenge.org. Participants will be provided with Docker templates and instructions to assist with their submissions. For reference, please refer to the SELMA3D 2025 Docker templates and instructions:

https://github.com/YingChen7/SELMA3D2025_example_algorithm/. We will offer step-by-step tutorials with images to guide participants through the process. Additionally, we will organize live Q&A sessions and webinars on containerization and deployment to assist teams that may lack expertise in this area. These initiatives aim to make the submission process smoother and more accessible for all participants.

In addition to the docker containers, each participating team is required to submit a 2-3 page summary outlining their methods and approaches along with the Docker container for the final test set submission. This summary is a mandatory part of the final test phase submission and is also necessary for co-authorship in the final challenge journal paper. Furthermore, based on our experience summarizing the SELMA3D 2024 submissions in the archive paper, we will provide more detailed guidelines on what participants should include in their summaries. For the self-supervised learning stage, the summary should cover the self-supervised learning strategy, and network architecture. For the fine-tuning stage, participants should describe the fine-tuning protocols, and provide a clear comparison of model performance with and without the self-supervised learning stage. These guidelines will ensure clarity and consistency across submissions.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will have access to some examples from the preliminary and final test sets without annotations. These examples can be used to test and validate their algorithms locally before official submission for evaluation. This allows participants to assess the performance of their methods and make any necessary adjustments prior to submitting them to the Grand Challenge.

To assess the benefits of self-supervised learning, each team will be required to submit solutions both with and without self-supervised pretraining. For each setting, teams may submit up to five entries for evaluation on the preliminary test set. Results on the preliminary test set will be displayed on a public leaderboard, serving as an initial and unofficial ranking. These evaluations allow participants to compare model performance with and without the self-supervised learning stage and to iteratively refine their methods.

It is important to note that the final rankings will be determined solely based on performance on the final test set. For this stage, each team will be granted one opportunity to submit a Docker container for evaluating their solutions both with and without self-supervised pretraining. In the event of technical issues, resubmission will be permitted; however, only the results from the final submission will be used to compute the official challenge

rankings.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Preliminary Schedule:

- Challenge website launch: April 1st, 2026
- Training set release: April 10th, 2026
- Release of preliminary test set samples (without annotation): June 1st, 2026
- Opening of submission and leaderboard for the preliminary test set: June 20th, 2026 - September 25th, 2026
- Release of final test set samples (without annotation): June 30st, 2026
- Opening of submission and leaderboard for the final test set: July 10th, 2026 - September 25th, 2026
- Contacting top-performing teams and planning for the in-person session: September 1st - September 26th, 2026 (teams requiring visas will be contacted earlier, and we will coordinate with MICCAI to send invitation letters for visa clearance.)
- In-person challenge event: October 4th or 8th, 2026

Additional point:

The performance results for both the preliminary and final test sets will be published immediately on the leaderboard upon submission via the Grand Challenge platform. The leaderboard will display the same evaluation scores that are shown to participants immediately after they submit their results. We will release the training set as early as possible, giving participants at least three months to develop their methods. Besides, we plan to conduct a series of both online and in-person seminars to promote the challenge and address any questions participants may have.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The data utilized in this task is a set of research data which consists of previously published data and data acquired by the challenge organizers within the ethics approval of specific studies [1-13]. As a result, the data has received approval from the pertinent ethical committee, and no further ethics approval is necessary. It is important to note that the data has been anonymized, with sample information removed.

References:

- [1] D. Kaltenecker, R. Al-Maskari, M. Negwer, et al. Virtual reality empowered deep learning analysis of brain activity. *Nature Methods*(21): 1306–1315, 2024 April.
- [2] S. Zhao, M.I. Todorov, R. Cai, et al. Cellular and molecular probing of intact human organs. *Cell* 180(4): 796-812, 2020 Feb.
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- [6] M. Belle, D. Godefroy, G. Couly, et al. Tridimensional visualization and analysis of early human development. *Cell* 169(1): 161-173, 2017 Mar.
- [7] H. Mai, Z. Rong, S. Zhao, et al. Scalable tissue labeling and clearing of intact human organs. *Nature Protocols* 17: 2188-2215, 2022 July.
- [8] Luo, M. Molbay, Y. Chen, et al. Nanocarrier imaging at single-cell resolution across entire mouse bodies with deep learning. *Nature Biotechnology*, 2025 Jan.
- [9] M.I. Todorov, J.C. Paetzold, O. Schoppe, et al. Machine learning analysis of whole mouse brain vasculature. *Nature Methods* 17: 442-449, 2020 Mar.
- [10] H. Mai, J. Luo, L. Hoeher, et al. Whole-body cellular mapping in mouse using standard IgG antibodies. *Nature Biotechnology* 42: 617–627, 2023 July.
- [11] M. Belle, D. Godefroy, C. Dominici, et al. A simple method for 3D analysis of immunolabeled axonal tracts in a transparent nervous system. *Cell reports* 9(4): 1191-1201, 2014 Nov.
- [12] <https://mab3d-atlas.com/validated-antibody-database>
- [13] Özen, Emine, et al. "Multicolor High Resolution SCAPE microscopy for Understanding Neural Connectivity." *Optics and the Brain*. Optica Publishing Group, 2025.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation code for the SELMA3D 2024 and 2025 challenge is publicly available on GitHub:

https://github.com/YingChen7/SELMA3D_challenge-evaluation/.

The evaluation code for SELMA3D 2026 will be accessible to the public on GitHub as well.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The submitted docker containers from all participants will be publicly accessible unless participants disagree.

Participants who do not agree to make docker public will not be eligible for awards, and will not be listed in the leaderboard.

Additionally, we strongly encourage participants to share their code with the public.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Monetary awards will not be provided.

Access to the preliminary and final test sets with annotations will be restricted to the main organizers and their annotation team exclusively.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE**Field(s) of application**

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research, Education, Training

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Semantic Segmentation (self/semi-supervised)

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort is 3D LSM images capturing a broad spectrum of biological structures with varying connectivity and spatial density from diverse specimens. A self-supervised learning strategy for LSM segmentation of these structures holds potential benefits across various segmentation applications for the whole organ or whole body.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge data cohort is 3D LSM images derived from mouse, macaque, and human samples. These images were produced by the Institute for Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine (iTERM), the Institute for Stroke and Dementia Research, the Institut de la Vision, Weill Cornell Medicine Helen & Robert Appel Alzheimer's Disease Research Institute and the Mortimer B. Zuckerman Mind Brain Behavior Institute between 2012 and 2025.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Light-sheet microscopy (LSM)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No contextual information will be made available.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No clinical information about the human samples will be made available.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The dataset encompasses 3D LSM images of samples obtained from mice, macaques, and humans following a tissue clearing protocol[1-5].

Individual specimen information will not be made available.

References:

[1] S. Zhao, M.I. Todorov, R. Cai, et al. Cellular and molecular probing of intact human organs. *Cell* 180(4): 796-812, 2020 Feb.

[2] A. Ertürk, K. Becker, N. Jährling, et al. Three-dimensional imaging of solvent-cleared organs using 3DISCO. *Nature Protocols* 7: 1983-1995, 2012 Nov.

[3] N. Renier, Z. Wu, D.J. Simon, et al. iDISCO: a simple, rapid method to immunolabel large tissue samples for volume imaging. *Cell* 159(4): 896-910, 2014 Nov.

[4] N Renier, EL Adams, C Kirst et al. Mapping of brain activity by automated volume analysis of immediate early genes. *Cell* 165(7): 1789-1802, 2016 June.

[5] Özen, Emine, et al. "Multicolor High Resolution SCAPE microscopy for Understanding Neural Connectivity." *Optics and the Brain*. Optica Publishing Group, 2025.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

This task focuses on a self-supervised learning strategy to develop a generalized model for semantic segmentation of diverse biological structures in 3D light-sheet microscopy (LSM) images.

To prevent participants from solely relying on the annotated training set for model training, thereby achieving favorable segmentation results without effectively utilizing the self-supervised learning stage, variations will be introduced between the annotated training set, preliminary test set, and final test set. The objective is to encourage the development of self-supervised learning strategies capable of pretraining models with robust generalization capabilities. Details of the unseen data introduced in preliminary test and final test sets, which differ from the training set, will be provided in the case definition section.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

LSM imaging from Ali Euturk's lab was performed using objective lens equipped with an immersion corrected dipping cap, mounted either on an UltraMicroscope II (LaVision BioTec, chamber size of $72 \times 74 \times 35$ mm, for small samples) or a prototype UltraMicroscope (Miltenyi Biotec, chamber size of $250 \times 90 \times 70$ mm, for large samples) coupled to a white light laser module (NKT SuperK Extreme EXW-12).

LSM imaging from Alain Chédotal's lab was performed with an ultramicroscope (LaVision BioTec) using InspectorPro software (LaVision BioTec) or a Blaze light-sheet microscope (Miltenyi Biotec) equipped with sCMOS camera 5.5MP (2560×2160 pixels) controlled by Inspector Pro 7.5.3 acquisition software (Miltenyi Biotec)

LSM imaging from Zhuhao Wu's lab was performed on a light-sheet microscope (Ultramicroscope II, LaVision Biotec) equipped with a sCMOS camera (Andor Neo) and a 2×/0.5 objective lens (MVPLAPO 2×) equipped with a 6 mm working distance dipping cap. Version v144 of the Inspector Microscope controller software was used.

LSM imaging for the CONNECTS project from Elizabeth Hillman's lab at Columbia University was acquired using a custom high-speed multicolor SCAPE (Swept Confocally Aligned Planar Excitation) microscope, specifically developed for large-scale, submicron-resolution imaging of brain sections. The system enables simultaneous multichannel imaging of cellular and cytoskeletal markers at high temporal throughput (up to 300 fps) and submicron spatial resolution ($0.4 \times 0.36 \times 0.26 \mu\text{m}^3$), supporting dense volumetric imaging of human and non-human primate brain tissue.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The data was obtained through the following procedure: structure staining, tissue clearing, LSM imaging.

Different fluorophores or antibodies were used to selectively bind to specific isolated structures in the sample, enhancing their visibility in the images.

Different tissue clearing methods were used following our previous work [1-5].

[1] S. Zhao, M.I. Todorov, R. Cai, et al. Cellular and molecular probing of intact human organs. *Cell* 180(4): 796-812, 2020 Feb.

[2] A. Ertürk, K. Becker, N. Jährling, et al. Three-dimensional imaging of solvent-cleared organs using 3DISCO. *Nature Protocols* 7: 1983-1995, 2012 Nov.

[3] N. Renier, Z. Wu, D.J. Simon, et al. iDISCO: a simple, rapid method to immunolabel large tissue samples for volume imaging. *Cell* 159(4): 896-910, 2014 Nov.

[4] N Renier, EL Adams, C Kirst et al. Mapping of brain activity by automated volume analysis of immediate early genes. *Cell* 165(7): 1789-1802, 2016 June.

[5] Özen, Emine, et al. "Multicolor High Resolution SCAPE microscopy for Understanding Neural Connectivity." *Optics and the Brain*. Optica Publishing Group, 2025.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

All raw image data were acquired from the Institute for Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine, the Institute for Stroke and Dementia Research, the Institut de la Vision, Weill Cornell Medicine Helen & Robert Appel Alzheimer's Disease Research Institute, the Mortimer B. Zuckerman Mind Brain Behavior Institute.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

The standardized imaging workflow, which includes structure staining, tissue clearing, and LSM imaging, was performed by experienced graduates and technicians who had undergone at least six months of training to master the process.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

In the unannotated subset of the training set designed for self-supervised learning, each case corresponds to a 3D patch cropped from a large 3D LSM image. The original 3D LSM images capture either entire organs or part of an organ from mouse, macaque, or human specimens. We cropped these large original 3D LSM images into patches, and filtered out the majority of non-informative patches. At the same time, a small representative subset of these background patches, approximately 5% per biological structure, is retained to preserve realistic imaging

conditions and support robustness assessment. The resulting patches constitute the cases used in this subset.

In the annotated subset of the training set, as well as in the preliminary and final test sets, each case consists of a 3D patch image cropped from the large 3D LSM image, accompanied by a corresponding voxel-wise annotation of the stained biological structures in the form of a 3D binary image.

All raw image patches are single-channel.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training subset with no annotations: (A total of around 35,050 patches of size 300×300×300 voxels)

1) for isolated structures (totally around 17,400 patches):

- ~5300 3D patches from 18 3D images of c-Fos+ cells [1]
- ~3400 3D patches from 4 3D images of cell nuclei [2]
- ~1600 3D patches from 4 3D images of amyloid-beta plaques [3]
- ~1100 3D patches from 1 3D image of Chondrocytes [4]
- ~1100 3D patches from 1 3D image of Chondrogenic cells [4]
- ~2500 3D patches from 1 3D image of Dopaminergic neurons [5]
- ~2400 3D patches from 1 3D image of Astrocytes [5]

2) for contiguous structures (totally around 17,650 patches)

- ~2600 3D patches from 9 3D images of blood vessels [6]
- ~800 3D patches from 4 3D images of arteries [7]
- ~2000 3D patches from 4 3D images of sympathetic nerves [7]
- ~ 4600 3D patches from 5 3D images of peripheral nerves (PGP9.5) [4, 5, 7, 8]
- ~650 3D patches from 4 3D images of lymphatic vessels [7]
- ~ 4500 3D patches from 2 3D images of Cranial nerves [4, 5]
- ~ 2500 3D patches from 8 3D images of axonal markers [9]

As these patches are cropped from whole organs or organisms, they encompass a wide range of structural densities. Information on the original volume corresponding to each patch will also be provided.

Training subset with annotations (A total of 82 patches of size 200×200×200 voxels):

1) for dense isolated structures (totally 18 patches)

- 9 3D patches of c-Fos+ cells [1]
- 9 3D patches of cell nuclei [2]

2) for sparse isolated structures (totally 20 patches)

- 20 3D patches of amyloid-beta plaques [3]

3) for dense contiguous structures (totally 16 patches)

- 16 3D patches of blood vessels [6]

4) for sparse contiguous structures (totally 28 patches)

- 16 3D patches of peripheral nerves [8]
- 12 3D patches of axonal markers [9]

Preliminary test set (A total of 26 patches of size 200×200×200 voxels):

1) for dense isolated structures (totally 5 patches)

- 1 3D patch of c-Fos+ cells [1]

- 1 3D patch of cell nuclei [2]
- 3 3D patches of microglia [10]
- 2)for sparse isolated structures (totally 7 patches)
 - 3 3D patches of amyloid-beta plaques [3]
 - 4 3D patches of fluorescent protein (EGFP) [11]
- 3) for dense contiguous structures (totally 6 patches)
 - 2 3D patches of blood vessels [6]
 - 4 3D patches of gut lymphatic vessels [7]
- 4)for sparse contiguous structures (totally 8 patches)
 - 2 3D patches of peripheral nerves [8]
 - 2 3D patches of axonal markers [9]
 - 4 3D patches of gut nerves [7]

Final test set (A total of 96 patches of size 200×200×200 voxels):

- 1) for dense isolated structures (totally 22 patches)
 - 5 3D patches of c-Fos+ cells [1]
 - 4 3D patches of cell nuclei [2]
 - 13 3D patches of microglia [10]
- 2) for sparse isolated structures (totally 24 patches)
 - 11 3D patches of amyloid-beta plaques [3]
 - 13 3D patches of fluorescent protein (EGFP) [11]
- 3) for dense contiguous structures (totally 22 patches)
 - 8 3D patches of blood vessels [6]
 - 14 3D patches of gut lymphatic vessels [7]
- 4)for sparse contiguous structures (totally 28 patches)
 - 8 3D patches of peripheral nerves [8]
 - 6 3D patches of axonal markers [9]
 - 14 3D patches of gut nerves [7]

References:

- [1] D. Kaltenecker, R. Al-Maskari, M. Negwer, et al. Virtual reality empowered deep learning analysis of brain activity. *Nature Methods*(21): 1306–1315, 2024 April.
- [2] S. Zhao, M.I. Todorov, R. Cai, et al. Cellular and molecular probing of intact human organs. *Cell* 180(4): 796-812, 2020 Feb.
- [3] H.S. Bhatia, A. Brunner, F. Öztürk, et al. Spatial proteomics in three-dimensional intact specimens. *Cell* 185(26): 5040-5058, 2022 Dec.
- [4] R. Blain, G. Couly, E. Shotar, et al. A tridimensional atlas of the developing human head. *Cell* 186(26): 5910-5924, 2023 Dec.
- [5] <https://mab3d-atlas.com/validated-antibody-database>
- [6] M.I. Todorov, J.C. Paetzold, O. Schoppe, et al. Machine learning analysis of whole mouse brain vasculature. *Nature Methods* 17: 442-449, 2020 Mar.
- [7] H. Mai, J. Luo, L. Hoeher, et al. Whole-body cellular mapping in mouse using standard IgG antibodies. *Nature Biotechnology* 42: 617–627, 2023 July.

- [8] R. Cai, C. Pan, A. Ghasemigharagoz, et al. Panoptic imaging of transparent mice reveals whole-body neuronal projections and skull-meninges connections. *Nature Neuroscience* 22: 317-327, 2019 Dec.
- [9] E. Özen, et al. "Multicolor High Resolution SCAPE microscopy for Understanding Neural Connectivity." *Optics and the Brain*. Optica Publishing Group, 2025.
- [10] H. Mai, Z. Rong, S. Zhao, et al. Scalable tissue labeling and clearing of intact human organs. *Nature Protocols* 17: 2188-2215, 2022 July.
- [11] Luo, M. Molbay, Y. Chen, et al. Nanocarrier imaging at single-cell resolution across entire mouse bodies with deep learning. *Nature Biotechnology*, 2025 Jan.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

In the annotated training set, 90% of the patches are already annotated, while in the test set, 95% of patches are already annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The images in the training set are sourced from our previously published works. A thorough inspection and verification process is meticulously carried out on all images to ensure their quality. The provided images encompass a wide range of biological structures within LSM images, capturing significant variability.

In the preliminary and final test sets, less than half of the patches correspond to biological structures also present in the training set. The remainder consists of new unseen biological structures. Performance on these test sets will provide insights into the model's ability to generalize to unseen structures.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

None

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

In the training set, the unannotated subset consists of informative patches from large 3D LSM images showcasing a diverse range of biological structures from mouse, macaque, or human specimens. This unannotated data is designed for pretraining models using self-supervised learning techniques. Additionally, we provide a much smaller annotated subset, comprising image patches with precise voxel-wise labels of these structures, to enable participants to fine-tune their models for segmentation tasks.

In the preliminary test set, fewer than 50% of the patches contain structures seen in the training set, while the majority ($\geq 50\%$) introduce new structures for both dense isolated, sparse isolated, dense contiguous and sparse contiguous structure types. This composition allows participants to assess their algorithms' performance on both seen structures and unseen structures. By using this setup, participants gain insights into how well their models generalize to unseen data while also validating their performance on previously seen structures.

The final test set maintains a similar distribution, with over 50% of patches representing previously unseen structures. This intentional imbalance ensures a robust evaluation of the model's ability to generalize to completely new data, a critical goal of self-supervised learning. By focusing on unseen structures, the final test set provides a more rigorous test of the participants' algorithms and emphasizes the core of the challenge, that is to

develop self-supervised learning methods for robust and generalizable segmentation.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The manual annotation and verification processes are conducted in 3D using virtual reality (VR) for visualization efficiency. Each case undergoes a hierarchical annotation process, beginning with initial semantic segmentation annotations, which are manually performed by an expert annotator with experience in LSM imaging. Two expert annotators participated in this stage. After the initial annotation, an expert with extensive LSM imaging experience verifies and refines the annotations. Additionally, two leaders from our organizing team conduct a thorough review of all annotations to ensure their accuracy and reliability.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The initial 3D manual annotations were crafted from scratch using virtual reality (VR) by annotators who underwent a minimum of three months of specialized training. For each image patch, which contains a single kind of biological structure, the annotators were asked to voxel-wisely label that biological structure with a value of 1, while assigning a value of 0 to the rest background. After the initial annotation process, additional manual refinements were carried out in 3D using VR, incorporating feedback from LSM imaging experts and team leaders to ensure accuracy and consistency.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Initial manual annotations are independently performed by two expert annotators with extensive biological and anatomical training, ensuring a thorough understanding of LSM data. For a representative subset of the dataset, these independent annotations are retained to assess inter-observer variability. Agreement is quantified using the same metrics applied during model evaluation, providing an empirical estimate of annotation uncertainty. The resulting inter-observer variability will be reported when the preliminary and final test submissions are opened.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Based on the initial annotations, discrepancies between annotations are reviewed and refined by an expert with three years of professional experience in LSM. The final consensus annotations are then determined and approved by two senior leaders with five or more years of professional experience in LSM.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For the unannotated subset of the training set used in self-supervised learning, the original 3D LSM images are first cropped into patches of size 300×300×300 voxels. Non-informative patches containing predominantly or

exclusively background are largely removed, while a small representative subset, which is approximately 5% per biological structure, is retained to preserve realistic low-signal conditions and enable robustness evaluation.. The remaining patches form the final unannotated subset, with each patch stored in 16-bit signed MHA (MetalImage) format.

For the annotated subset of the training set, as well as the preliminary and final test sets, small patches extracted from the large 3D image, accompanied by their corresponding annotations, are stored in MHA (MetalImage) format with 16-bit signed precision.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Our annotation process follows a hierarchical structure with multiple levels of verification and approval. Due to the significant time and effort required to annotate a single case, we do not have multiple annotations for the same case from different annotators, and as a result, we are unable to provide inter- and intra-annotator variability. Notably, an expert with extensive LSM imaging experience, along with two leaders from our organizing team, collaboratively review and either approve or revise the annotations. As these three individuals work together to assess and finalize the annotations, our goal is to ensure their accuracy and reliability.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

We aim to minimize the number of artifacts in our images. However, stripes are a common type of artifact found in LSM images[1]. These artifacts can lead to over- or under-segmentation errors.

[1] J. Mayer, A. Robert-Moreno, J. Sharpe, J. Swoger. Attenuation artifacts in light sheet fluorescence microscopy corrected by OPTiSPIM. *Light: Science & Applications* 7: 70, 2018 Oct.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

During the model evaluation, we will separately evaluate the model's performance on isolated structures and contiguous structures.

For assessing segmentation results of both dense isolated and sparse isolated structures, two metrics will be employed:

- 1) volumetric Dice similarity coefficients (DSC)
- 2) Panoptic Quality (PQ) [1]

For assessing segmentation results of both dense contiguous and sparse contiguous structures, again two metrics will be employed:

- 1) volumetric Dice similarity coefficients (DSC)
- 2) Centerline-Dice similarity coefficients (cDice) [2]

[1] Kofler, F., Möller, H., Buchner, J., et al. (2023). Panoptica: Instance-wise Evaluation of 3D Semantic and Instance Segmentation Maps. arXiv preprint arXiv:2312.02608.

[2] S. Shit, J.C. Paetzold, A. Sekuboyina, et al. cDice - a novel topology-preserving loss function for tubular structure segmentation. In IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2021, pp. 16555-16564.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The selected metrics align with the recommendations of the Metrics Reloaded toolkit [1]. The volumetric Dice similarity coefficient is a widely used metric to assess the overall overlap between the ground truth and the predicted segmentation. It calculates the similarity of two sets by comparing the shared voxel volume relative to the total voxel volume, providing a global measure of segmentation accuracy.

For the segmentation of isolated structures, the primary objective is to accurately identify each individual component. Panoptic Quality (PQ) offers a holistic evaluation by jointly measuring recognition quality (how well distinct components are correctly identified) and segmentation quality (how accurately their shapes are delineated). As a result, PQ provides a comprehensive metric for assessing both instance segmentation performance and overall semantic structure identification.

For the segmentation of contiguous structures, centerline-Dice further evaluates the voxel-wise overlap of the central axis of contiguous structures. cDice helps assess how well the centerline of the predicted structure matches the centerline of the ground truth, offering a clear measure of how much of the contiguous structure is correctly identified and captured.

[1] L. Maier-Hein, A. Reinke, P. Godau, et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nature Methods 21: 195–212, 2024 Feb.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

The ranking of a submitted algorithm is determined through the following process:

- Compute the metric scores for each test case;
- Calculate the average of the metric scores across all test cases for each individual metric;
- Rank the averaged scores for each metric independently based on its specific optimization trend (e.g., higher is better or lower is better);
- Determine the ranking of the submitted algorithm by calculating the mean rank across all metrics separately for dense isolated, sparse isolated, dense contiguous and sparse contiguous structures;
- Determine the overall ranking of the submitted algorithm by calculating the mean rank across two structure

types;

- If two or more algorithms have equal final ranks, the prize will be shared equally among them.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results are prevented by design in the Grand Challenge setup, as validated in our previous two challenge editions. All participants are required to submit solutions that successfully generate predictions for every test case; only submissions that complete inference on all cases are considered valid.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

There is no interdependence between test cases. While multiple test cases may originate from the same 3D LSM image, there is no overlap between any two test cases. To evaluate algorithm performance, various metrics are calculated independently for each test case.

We adhere to the recommendations of L. Maier-Hein et al. [1] for determining the final ranking of algorithms. In general, there are two primary ranking schemes for aggregating metric scores across test cases. The first scheme is metric-based aggregation or aggregate-then-rank, which means metric scores are first aggregated across all test cases using statistical measures such as the mean or median. Algorithms are then ranked based on the aggregated score. The second scheme is case-based aggregation or rank-then-aggregate. In this scheme, each test case is ranked individually, and the final rank of an algorithm is determined by aggregating the ranks across all test cases.

According to L. Maier-Hein et al [1], single-metric rankings exhibit greater statistical robustness when metric-based aggregation is employed and when the mean is used instead of the median for aggregation. This scheme ensures more reliable comparisons between algorithms.

[1] L. Maier-Hein, Matthias Eisenmann, Annika Reinke, et al. Why rankings of biomedical image analysis competitions should be interpreted with care. Nature communications 9: 1-13, 2018 Dec.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

We will employ resampling-based statistical analyses, including bootstrapping and leave-one-out (LOO) analyses, to assess the robustness and stability of algorithm performance estimates and rankings, following the recommendations of Maier-Hein et al. [1].

Bootstrapping is used to estimate uncertainty in performance metrics, which is particularly suitable given the heterogeneous nature of our test data. Leave-one-out analyses are applied to evaluate the sensitivity of rankings to individual test cases and to assess ranking stability.

To account for dependencies among patches extracted from the same LSM volume, all resampling (bootstrapping and LOO) is performed at the volume level, rather than at the individual patch level. This ensures that intra-volume correlations are preserved.

[1] L. Maier-Hein, Matthias Eisenmann, Annika Reinke, et al. Why rankings of biomedical image analysis competitions should be interpreted with care. Nature communications 9: 1-13, 2018 Dec.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

The precision of performance estimates for individual algorithms will be assessed using percentile-based bootstrap confidence intervals computed on the test set while accounting for the presence of multiple biological structure types. Bootstrap resampling is performed either stratified by biological structures or separately within each structure, and 95% confidence intervals are derived from the empirical distributions of the bootstrapped performance estimates. This approach provides a robust and structure-aware quantification of uncertainty.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Performance variability across test cases is assessed by analyzing the distribution of case-wise performance values. Variability is summarized using standard deviation and interquartile range (IQR), and visualized using distribution plots such as boxplots and violin plots. In addition, leave-one-out analyses are used to assess the influence of individual cases on overall performance.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Variability of rankings is assessed using bootstrapped and leave-one-out ranking analyses, as proposed by Maier-Hein et al [1], while accounting for the presence of multiple biological structures in the test set. Rankings are recomputed for each bootstrap sample and each leave-one-out iteration, either in a structure-stratified manner or separately for each structure, and the resulting ranking distributions are analyzed to quantify ranking stability and sensitivity to both individual test cases and biological structures. For clarity, we will report confidence intervals of the rankings for each algorithm, allowing top-performing methods to be compared not only by mean rank but also by the range of variability observed across resampling iterations.

[1] L. Maier-Hein, Matthias Eisenmann, Annika Reinke, et al. Why rankings of biomedical image analysis competitions should be interpreted with care. Nature communications 9: 1-13, 2018 Dec.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Statistical significance of performance differences between algorithms is assessed using resampling-based, non-parametric tests applied to the bootstrapped performance metrics. Comparisons are performed for each structure type individually as well as for overall performance. For top-performing methods, we will explicitly report both confidence intervals and p-values derived from these resampling analyses, indicating whether observed differences are consistently significant across bootstrap iterations.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Missing data are prevented by design in the Grand Challenge setup, as validated in our previous two challenge editions.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

All statistical analyses, including bootstrapping and leave-one-out ranking analyses, will be performed using open-source Python libraries such as NumPy, SciPy, pandas, and scikit-learn.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

The preliminary and final test sets include newly introduced structures not present in the annotated training set. To evaluate the generalization capability of the semantic segmentation models, we will separately assess segmentation performance for both seen and unseen structures. This analysis will highlight any variations in performance on the newly introduced structures compared to those included in the training set. By designing the challenge this way, we aim to motivate participants to prioritize self-supervised learning approaches that enhance model generalization.

Moreover, to complement patch-level evaluation, we will perform volume-level analyses to assess spatial coherence across larger regions, especially for continuous structures. As the gut nerves and gut lymphatic vessels in the testing set are cropped from the larger volumes, predictions from adjacent patches will be assembled to reconstruct these larger volumes. Performance will then be evaluated on the reconstructed volumes, focusing on spatial consistency, boundary continuity, and anatomical plausibility across regions. This analysis provides complementary insights beyond per-patch metrics, allowing evaluation of models' ability to capture long-range spatial structures.

TASK 2: Self-supervised learning for 3D LSM image segmentation under open data conditions

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

While Task 1 focuses on self-supervised learning (SSL) strategies for 3D LSM image segmentation under fixed training data conditions, Task 2 is dedicated to studying the data scaling effects when applying SSL to light-sheet microscopy domain. In contrast to Task 1, participants in Task 2 are allowed to leverage arbitrary amounts of data for SSL. We will provide access to the full set of original unannotated 3D LSM images used in Task 1, but before any cropping or preprocessing. Participants may therefore explore their own preprocessing or curation pipelines to construct pretraining datasets for SSL. Moreover, participants are encouraged to incorporate any additional public or private LSM data.

The annotated training set provided by us will remain the same as in Task 1, and the finetuning stage is constrained to use only this annotated training set, without any external annotated data. This constraint ensures that the performance gains can be attributed to data scaling in SSL rather than to additional supervision from extra annotations.

Overall, Task 2 offers greater flexibility for participants to explore data curation, scaling and their impact on SSL strategies.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Light-sheet microscopy, 3D image, deep learning, self-supervised learning, image segmentation, isolated structure, contiguous structure, sparse structure, dense structure, data scaling, data engineering

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Same as Task 1

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Same as Task 1

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

No

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event as open call challenge

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

Same as Task 1

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

Same as Task 1

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

Same as Task 1

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

User interaction is permitted for curating additional training data for self-supervised learning beyond the datasets we provide. As in Task 1, user interaction is also allowed during data preprocessing.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Besides the unannotated data provided by us, participants are free to introduce any additional public or private unannotated LSM data for pretraining. Participants must precisely document the external data. They must describe which data, how much external data, and how they (pre-) processed the data. Participants are encouraged to train a baseline on no external data to quantify the performance impact of the external data.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Same as Task 1

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Same as Task 1

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

This is the first time that SELMA3D introduces an open-data task. Through this task, we aim to encourage participants to explore the data-scaling effects of self-supervised learning (SSL) strategies on LSM images by incorporating external datasets beyond those we provide. We will collaborate with participants to summarize the key findings from this task, which will form a dedicated section in the same journal article reporting the results of Task 1 and previous challenge editions. All participating teams that submit work contributing to this task are welcome to contribute to our challenge publication. Up to three authors from each participating team will be acknowledged as authors of the article. Any additional authors from the submissions may be included upon request according to the ICMJE authorship guidelines.

Furthermore, we encourage all participating teams to independently submit their results without imposing any publication embargo.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Same as Task 1

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will have access to the same examples from the preliminary and final test sets without annotations as in Task 1. These examples can be used to test and validate their algorithms locally before official submission for evaluation.

As this task focuses on investigating data-scaling effects, participating teams are encouraged to submit models pretrained with self-supervised learning on datasets of varying scales. Each team may submit up to five entries to the preliminary test set. The corresponding results will be displayed on a public leaderboard, serving as an initial and unofficial ranking. This stage enables participants to assess the impact of data scale on model performance.

Final rankings will be determined exclusively based on performance on the final test set. At this stage, each team may submit up to two Docker containers for evaluation under different data-scale settings. In case of technical issues, resubmissions will be permitted; however, only the results from the final valid submission will be used to determine the official challenge rankings.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Same as Task 1

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The ethical approval for the data provided by our team is the same as in Task 1. Participants are required to submit documentation or a reference to the document of ethical approval for any external data used in their submissions.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)

- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Same as Task 1

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Same as Task 1

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Same as Task 1

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research, Education, Training

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Semantic Segmentation (self/semi-supervised)

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Same as Task 1

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

While the challenge cohort of data provided by us remains the same as in Task 1, participants may introduce additional 3D LSM images from diverse specimens and biological structures. Participants are required to provide relevant details and documentation for any external datasets used.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Same as Task 1

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Same as Task 1

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Same as Task 1

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data origin of the dataset we provide is the same as in Task 1. Participants must disclose the source of any external datasets used in their submissions.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Same as Task 1

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The data acquisition devices for the dataset we provide are the same as in Task 1. Participants must specify the acquisition devices used for any external datasets included in their submissions.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The data acquisition details for the dataset we provide are the same as in Task 1. Participants must provide documentations of the acquisition details used for any external datasets included in their submissions.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The data acquisition centers for the dataset we provide are the same as in Task 1. Participants must specify the acquisition centers of any external datasets included in their submissions.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

The characteristics of the subjects involved in data acquisition for the dataset we provide are the same as in Task 1. Participants must report the corresponding information for any external datasets used in their submissions.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Different from Task 1, we are now providing the original 3D LSM image files in Task 2. Accordingly, in the unannotated subset of the training set, each case comprises a large 3D LSM image capturing either the full organ or part of an organ from mouse, macaque, or human specimens. The annotated sets used for training, preliminary testing and final testing remain the same as in Task 2, so does the case definition.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The training set with no annotation for self-supervised learning are the original 3D LSM images where the unannotated patches in Task 1 come from. This set contains a total of 66 large 3D LSM images. In detail, these images are:

1) for isolated structures (totally 30 images, each exceeding 4×10^{10} voxels, amounting to over 44,000 patches of size $300 \times 300 \times 300$ voxels):

- 18 3D images of c-Fos+ cells [1]
- 4 3D images of cell nuclei [2]
- 4 3D images of amyloid-beta plaques [3]
- 1 3D image of Chondrocytes [4]
- 1 3D image of Chondrogenic cells [4]
- 1 3D image of Dopaminergic neurons [5]
- 1 3D image of Astrocytes [5]

2) for contiguous structures (totally 36 images, each exceeding 3×10^{10} voxels, amounting to over 40,000 patches of size $300 \times 300 \times 300$ voxels)

- 9 3D images of blood vessels [6]

- 4 3D images of arteries [7]
- 4 3D images of sympathetic nerves [7]
- 5 3D images of peripheral nerves (PGP9.5) [4, 5, 7, 8]
- 4 3D images of lymphatic vessels [7]
- 2 3D images of Cranial nerves [4, 5]
- 8 3D images of axonal markers [9]

The annotated cases in the training, preliminary test and final test sets are the same as in Task 1.

References:

- [1] D. Kaltenecker, R. Al-Maskari, M. Negwer, et al. Virtual reality empowered deep learning analysis of brain activity. *Nature Methods*(21): 1306–1315, 2024 April.
- [2] S. Zhao, M.I. Todorov, R. Cai, et al. Cellular and molecular probing of intact human organs. *Cell* 180(4): 796-812, 2020 Feb.
- [3] H.S. Bhatia, A. Brunner, F. Öztürk, et al. Spatial proteomics in three-dimensional intact specimens. *Cell* 185(26): 5040-5058, 2022 Dec.
- [4] R. Blain, G. Couly, E. Shotar, et al. A tridimensional atlas of the developing human head. *Cell* 186(26): 5910-5924, 2023 Dec.
- [5] <https://mab3d-atlas.com/validated-antibody-database>
- [6] M.I. Todorov, J.C. Paetzold, O. Schoppe, et al. Machine learning analysis of whole mouse brain vasculature. *Nature Methods* 17: 442-449, 2020 Mar.
- [7] H. Mai, J. Luo, L. Hoeher, et al. Whole-body cellular mapping in mouse using standard IgG antibodies. *Nature Biotechnology* 42: 617–627, 2023 July.
- [8] R. Cai, C. Pan, A. Ghasemigharagoz, et al. Panoptic imaging of transparent mice reveals whole-body neuronal projections and skull-meninges connections. *Nature Neuroscience* 22: 317-327, 2019 Dec.
- [9] E. Özen, et al. "Multicolor High Resolution SCAPE microscopy for Understanding Neural Connectivity." *Optics and the Brain*. Optica Publishing Group, 2025.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

Same as Task 1

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

As this task focuses on investigating data-scaling effects in self-supervised learning, participating teams are encouraged to incorporate external datasets or apply their own preprocessing and data selection strategies during the pretraining stage. However, the annotated dataset for supervised fine-tuning must remain the same as in Task 1 to ensure a fair comparison.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

None

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Same as Task 1

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Same as Task 1

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Same as Task 1

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Same as Task 1

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Same as Task 1

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

In Task 2, the unannotated subset of the training set for self-supervised learning will consist of the original 3D LSM images provided by us. Due to the large size of each 3D LSM volume, individual 2D planes are stored as 16-bit signed TIFF files.

The annotated training subset, as well as the preliminary and final test sets, will remain identical to those used in Task 1.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Same as Task 1

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Same as Task 1

ASSESSMENT METHODS**Metric(s)**

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Same as Task 1

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Same as Task 1

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Same as Task 1

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Same as Task 1

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Same as Task 1

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Same as Task 1

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Same as Task 1

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Same as Task 1

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Same as Task 1

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Same as Task 1

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Same as Task 1

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Same as Task 1

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

In addition to the analyses conducted in Task 1, this task will include a dedicated analysis of data-scaling effects. Specifically, we will compare the performance of the same self-supervised learning (SSL) strategy under different data scales, examining how segmentation performance varies across structure groups and individual structures, as well as with respect to the scale ratio of each structural category.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

References are inserted in-place for the relevant text-fields.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

None